

Study on Chemical and Thermal Properties of Bamboo Fiber Mat/Nano Silica Reinforced Epoxy/Palm Oil Bio Composites

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of bamboo fiber mats and nano silica as reinforcing agents in palm oil-based epoxy resin composites. Thirteen different compositions were fabricated, varying the number of bamboo fiber layers and the weight percentage of nano silica. The thermal conductivity, density and biodegradability were evaluated. The composite containing 3 layers of bamboo fiber mat and 5% nano silica exhibited the best overall performance. FTIR analysis confirmed similar spectral patterns across all samples. Sample C9 showed the highest thermal stability, losing 67% less weight than others in TGA. The combination of bamboo fibers, nano silica, and palm oil epoxy resulted in a composite with improved physical, chemical, and thermal properties. This sustainable approach offers a promising alternative to petroleum-based resins for various applications. These results suggest that bamboo fiber-reinforced epoxy composites can be a sustainable and high-performance material for various applications, such as food packaging, door panels, and lightweight structures.

Keywords: Biocomposites, Palm oil, Bamboo fiber mat, Nano silica, TGA, FTIR

1. Introduction

The increasing focus on environmental sustainability and the search for alternative materials has led to growing interest in bio-composites across various industries. These materials, which are typically made from natural fibers and plant-based resins, offer a promising alternative to traditional composites that rely heavily on synthetic fibers and petroleum-based polymers[1,2]. Among natural fibers, bamboo stands out due to its strength, fast growth, and abundance. Nano-silica particles, when added to composites, can significantly improve their

mechanical, chemical, and thermal properties. This is because of their large surface area and strong interaction with polymer matrices[3,4].

Epoxy resin, a widely used thermosetting polymer, is known for its excellent heat resistance and ability to withstand contaminants. In recent years, there have been successful attempts to incorporate various plant-based oils, such as soybean oil, castor oil, and annona squamosa, oil, into epoxy resin as a component[5–7]

Palm oil, particularly in countries like India, offers a promising opportunity due to its abundance and sustainable supply. The development of epoxidised palm oil (EPO) as a new derivative product could create new market opportunities for value-added palm oil products[8–10]. There is still limited research on epoxy composites reinforced with bamboo fiber mats and nano-silica, especially when combined with palm oil-derived biomaterials. Although epoxy-based composites have been extensively studied, our understanding of how palm oil-based bio-resins can optimize their physical, chemical, and thermal properties is limited[10].

This study aims to address this knowledge gap by developing and characterizing a new bio-composite made of bamboo fiber mat, nano-silica, and a palm oil-based epoxy matrix. The goal is to fabricate and investigate the density, Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR), thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA), and biodegradability characteristics of the palm oil/epoxy and bamboo fiber mat/nano-silica biocomposites.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Palm oil was obtained from Shree Western G & C Industries and Saj International Exports. The epoxy matrix and hardener (HY 951, araldite) were sourced from M/s Seenivasa Solutions, Pondicherry, India. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was purchased from Indian Scientific Solution, India. Bamboo fiber mats with an aerial density of 240 GSM and a thickness of 0.34 mm were provided by Metro Composites, Pvt. Ltd., Tamil Nadu, India.

2.2 Alkaline Treatment of Bamboo Fiber Mats

The bamboo fiber mats were subjected to a thorough treatment process. First, they were cleaned with pressurized water for one hour to remove organic matter and fine particles. Then, they were dried in the sun for two days. Next, the mats were soaked in distilled water at room temperature and then oven-dried at 110°C for 24 hours. Finally, they were immersed in a 5 wt% NaOH solution for 24 hours and then oven-dried again at 110°C for 24 hours.

This treatment was intended to increase the surface area of the bamboo fiber mats and reduce the number of hydrophilic groups. This would improve their compatibility with the hydrophobic polymer matrix and enhance the adhesion between the fiber mats and the matrix.[11,12].

2.3 Fabrication of Biocomposites

Thirteen biocomposite samples were created with different combinations of nano-silica and bamboo fiber mats. The process started by evenly dispersing nano-silica particles in the epoxy-palm oil matrix. Biocomposites were then made using a hand lay-up mold (300 x 300 x 3 mm). For multi-layer composites, NaOH-treated fiber mats (10.5 wt%) were added one by one. The samples were cured at room temperature for 24 hours and then post-cured at 120°C for 48 hours, following methods from previous research [13,14]. This process was repeated to produce biocomposite laminates with different amounts of nano-silica (0, 3, 5, and 7 wt%) and bamboo fiber mat layers (0, 2, 3, and 4). The names and compositions of the resulting nano-biocomposites are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1 Bamboo fiber mats / nano silica particles reinforced with palm oil and epoxy biocomposites

Table 1 Composition of bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites

S.No	Composite designation	Epoxy & Palm oil wt%	Bamboo fiber mat (0, 2, 3 & 4 layer)	Nano silica (wt%) (0 %, 3%, 5% & 7%)
1	C1	70 % + 30 %	0 (0 wt %)	0
2	C2	59.5 % + 30 %	2 (10.5 wt %)	0
3	C3	59.5 % + 27 %	2 (10.5 wt %)	3
4	C4	59.5 % + 25 %	2 (10.5 wt %)	5
5	C5	59.5 % + 23 %	2 (10.5 wt %)	7
6	C6	54.25 % + 30 %	3 (15.75 wt %)	0
7	C7	54.25 % + 27 %	3 (15.75 wt %)	3
8	C8	54.25 % + 25 %	3 (15.75 wt %)	5
9	C9	54.25 % + 23 %	3 (15.75 wt %)	7
10	C10	49 % + 30 %	4 (21 wt %)	0
11	C11	49 % + 27 %	4 (21 wt %)	3
12	C12	49 % + 25 %	4 (21 wt %)	5
13	C13	49 % + 23 %	4 (21 wt %)	7

2.4 Characterization Techniques

2.4.1 Density Measurement

To determine the density of the biocomposites, the water displacement method was used. The samples were completely submerged in water, and the volume of water they displaced was measured. This volume was then used to calculate the density by dividing the weight of the sample by its volume.

2.4.2 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

FT-IR measurements were performed using a Bruker IFS 66 infrared spectrophotometer at the Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University. The KBr pellet technique was used to

prepare the samples for analysis. Spectra were collected with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} over the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Before each sample, a background spectrum was recorded to ensure accurate results. The KBr used was dried in an oven to reduce water interference.

2.4.3 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Thermal analysis of the biocomposites was conducted using a NETZSCH STA 449F3 at the Department of Physics, Annamalai University. Samples weighing 10 grams were heated in a platinum pan under a nitrogen atmosphere from 27°C to 597°C at a heating rate of 5°C per minute. This was done to evaluate the thermal stability and degradation of the biocomposites.

2.4.4 Biodegradability Test

The biodegradability of the samples was assessed through a soil burial test. The samples were initially weighed, then buried in soil for 60 days. After this period, they were retrieved, cleaned with tissue paper, and weighed again. The weight loss, calculated as the difference between the initial and final weights, served as an indicator of biodegradation. The percentage weight loss was calculated using the following equation:

$$W (\%) = \{(W_{in} - W_{fi}) / W_{in}\} \times 100\%$$

Where W_{in} and W_{fi} are the initial and final weights of specimens, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Density Analysis of Bamboo Fiber Mat Nano Biocomposites

Figure 2 shows that the density of the biocomposites increased with the addition of bamboo fiber layers and nano-silica particles. The highest density (2.4 g/cm^3) was achieved with four bamboo fiber layers and 5 wt% nano-silica. However, further increases in nano-silica concentration led to a slight decrease in density. The density of biocomposites is influenced by factors such as fiber content, nanoparticle content, orientation, and compaction during manufacturing. While high-density composites generally exhibit better mechanical and thermal properties, excessive nano-silica can lead to a decrease in density due to factors like porosity and changes in the composite's structure [15,16].

Figure 2 Density obtained for bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites

3.2 FT-IR Analysis of Bamboo Fiber Mat Nano Biocomposites

The chemical groups present in the bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites are listed in Table 2. A detailed comparative FT-IR analysis was performed on biocomposites with 2, 3, and 4 layers of bamboo fiber and varying amounts of nano-silica (0, 3, 5, and 7 wt%) (Figure 3(a–c)). The results showed that the spectra of all the nano biocomposites were highly similar, and Table 2 identifies the specific chemical groups [14,17,18].

Figure 3 FT-IR for bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites

Table 2: Identities of the Chemical Groups For Bamboo Fiber Mat Nano Biocomposites

**FT-IR frequency
Bamboo fiber mat**

S.No	0 layer	2 layer				3 layer				4 layer				Vibrational assignment	
	Nano silica (wt%)														
	0%	0%	3%	5%	7%	0%	3%	5%	7%	0%	3%	5%	7%		
	Sample Name														
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13		
1	3322 br s	3382 br s	3392 br s	3402 br s	3404 br s	3396 br s	3384 br s	3399 br s	3402 br s	3384 br s	3394 br s	3388 br s	3406 br s	O-H Stretching	
2	2986 s	2965 s	2968 s	2962 s	2974 s	2981 s	2966 s	2982 s	2972 s	2964 s	2972 s	2984 s	2968 s	CH ₂ Stretching	
3	2762 w	2756 w	2754 w	2758 w	2751 w	2754 w	2756 w	2762 w	2766 w	2744 w	2758 w	2758 w	2766 w	CH ₂ Stretching	
4	1742 m	1744 m	1745 m	1745 m	1746 m	1751 m	1750 m	1748 m	1742 m	1754 m	1756 m	1748 m	1747 m	C=O Stretching	
5	1598 m	1592 m	1596 m	1598 m	1602 m	1606 m	1607 m	1608 m	1602 m	1602 m	1604 m	1608 m	1602 m	C=C Stretching	
6	1509 vs	1509 vs	1510 vs	1510 vs	1510 vs	1509 vs	1509 vs	1510 vs	1512 vs	1512 vs	1509 vs	1514 vs	1516 vs	C=C Stretching	
7	1359 s	1360 m	1360 m	1361 m	1361 m	1359 m	1361 m	1361 m	1364 m	1376 m	1368 m	1369 m	1372 m	C-C Stretching	
8	1190 w	1190 w	1190 w	1188 w	1186 w	1186 w	1186 w	1188 w	1192 w	1186 w	1172 w	1198 w	1196 w	C-O Stretching	
9	1146 s	1147 s	1148 s	1148 s	1148 s	1247 s	1147 s	1148 s	1144 s	1148 s	1145 s	1152 s	1148 s	C-O Stretching	
10	1082 s	1081 s	1071 s	1074 s	1078 s	1079 s	1181 s	Ar. C-H Scissoring							
11	1038 m	1038 m	1040 m	1040 m	1042 m	1039 m	1039 m	1040 m	1040 m	1040 m	1042 m	1039 m	1042 m	Ar. C-H Inplane Bending	
13	789 vs	802 s	809 s	809 s	809 s	809 s	804 s	802 s	804 s	805 s	803 s	802 s	803 s	C-C-C Inplane Bnding	

3.3 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Figure 4 TGA for bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites

TGA analysis of the C1-C13 bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites showed different thermal stability profiles. The C9 sample, which had three layers of bamboo fiber mat and 7 wt% nano-silica, had the highest thermal stability. All composites showed good thermal resistance, with only 2.5-8% weight loss at 230°C. The initial weight loss, around 22%, happened between 290-350°C due to the loss of moisture and the breakdown of cellulose and hemicellulose. A more significant weight loss, from 350-482°C, was caused by the breakdown of hemicelluloses, cellulose, and lignin[19]. Complete decomposition of the combustible components and the formation of char occurred at 510°C. The total weight loss for the C1-C13 composites ranged from 79.4 to 88.2 wt%, with C9 showing the lowest weight loss (79.4%). These results demonstrate the thermal behavior and stability of bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites, offering important information for potential uses in environments with high thermal requirements[20].

3.4 Biodegradability Testing

Figure 5 Biodegradability for bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites

The biodegradability of the bamboo fiber mat nano biocomposites decreased as the number of bamboo fiber mat layers and the weight percentage of nano-silica reinforcement increased. Composites reinforced with two fiber mat layers were more biodegradable than those with three and four mat layers. This decrease in biodegradability can be attributed to the increased number of bamboo fiber mat layers and higher weight percentage of nano-silica reinforcement, which create a more compact, less porous, and chemically stable composite material. These factors together reduce the composite material's biodegradability by limiting the contact between micro and macro organisms and the composite samples over a longer period[21,22].

4. Conclusions

This study evaluated palm oil-blend epoxy resin biocomposites reinforced with bamboo fiber mats and nano-silica. The C8 composite, with three bamboo fiber layers and 5 wt% nano-silica, had the highest density. FT-IR analysis confirmed the presence of cellulose and lignin. Thermogravimetric analysis showed the C9 nano-silica biocomposite had excellent thermal stability. These results suggest potential applications in lightweight domestic products. The combination of natural bamboo fibers, nano-silica particles, and palm oil-based epoxy resin created a composite with improved physical, chemical, and thermal properties, offering a sustainable alternative to petroleum-based resins. This study successfully developed a novel biocomposite that balances performance and sustainability. The components' synergistic effect produced a material with promising characteristics for various applications. Future research should focus on optimizing processing methods, exploring other natural fibers and bio-resins, and conducting long-term durability tests to expand the potential of these eco-friendly composites in industrial applications.

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